

Selection Standards for National Teams: Theory and Practice

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Abstract : This article deals with selection standards for national sport teams. The author examines the legal framework for selection criteria and suggests using the most honest criteria.

Keywords : national teams, standards of forming teams, selection standards, sport legislations

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